

SOFT SKILLS DEVELOPMENT IN PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL AND ITS IMPLICATION TO PUPILS' LEARNING COMPETENCE

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Soft Skills Development in Public Elementary School and its Implication to Pupils' Learning Competence

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Abstract

The study attempted to ascertain the significant relationship between the level of pupils' learning competence and the extent of pupils' soft skills development in terms of personal, social, and communication skills. This study also utilized the descriptive-correlational research, and the Statistical tools used in the study were the mean and standard deviation to determine the extent of softskills development and frequency and percentage distribution were used to determine the level of pupils' learning competence. Pearson r was utilized to ascertain significant relationship between the level of pupils' learning competence and the extent of pupils' softskills development. Findings revealed that personal skills were "moderately developed"; social skills were "high developed"; and communication skills were "moderately developed". There were more pupils, 32 (46%) had satisfactory learning competence while only 2 or 3% had fairly satisfactory learning competence. Further, results on the correlation test suggests that softskills development in terms of personal, social, and communication skills denote "negligible correlation" with pupils' learning competence. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted. Subsequently, it was recommended that in teachers should be motivated to design, develop, and utilize their strategic intervention materials which are responsive to pupils' learning challenges and inclusive and individual learning needs.

Keywords: *soft skills development, personal, social, communication skills pupils' learning competence*

Introduction

Learning flinches from pupil's ability to deal with the necessary skills such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Teachers are tasked to develop the peculiar qualities of pupils that supports situational consciousness and enhances the pupils' ability to learn social and interactive skills, character traits, and the right attitude in their studies.

The study is anchored on the legal and philosophical underpinnings of the D.O. 21, series of 2019 also known as policy guidelines on the K to 12 Education Program which highlights the mastery of the personal and social skills of young learners. Further, the order emphasized the development of skills to holistically develop the 21st century learners.

The 21st century learners are expected to deal proficiently with multiple challenges and issues in life and in extricating glitches through appropriate resolutions which require their soft skills. With this, teachers, apart from the K-12 curriculum, are encouraged to develop pupils' ability to adjust to the world, improve personal, social, and communication skills.

With this quandary, teachers necessitate to intensify pupils' soft skills such as their ability to work with fellow learners, giving attention to details, verbal and written ability, emotional stability, malleability, suppleness, problem-solving, and relational skills. Inappropriately, these soft skills are often overlooked and untapped in school comprehensively which results to pitiable indexes of the anticipated soft skills among young learners.

Soft skills are personal attribute among pupils which intensifies school and classroom mindfulness and enhances their aptitude to improve school and learning performance. These are non-technical skills that describe how pupils perform their school and academic activities and how they interact with others.

Consequently, teachers should change the teaching emphasis to the development of pupils' soft skills because these are indispensable to learning success. Indeed, soft skills are a phrase closely related to life skills, deals with interpersonal skills, emotional intelligence, and social skills. Soft skills are devised which means life skills, social skills, interpersonal skills, personal characteristics, attributes, and personality to admirably adapt according to the needs and desires of others.

Zahid and Hassan (2020) asserted that teachers should change the teaching focus to soft skills, because in this twenty-first century those skills are essential to individual pupil's success. Additionally, it was pointed out that soft skills are phrase closely related to life skills which deals with interpersonal skills, emotional intelligence, social skills, personal characteristics, attributes, and personality to admirably adapt according to the needs and desires of pupils.

Conversely, the teaching focuses only on the mastery of the basic competencies in each learning areas setting aside the development of soft skills to pupils in public elementary schools. It is based on the earlier-stated circumstance that the researcher is motivated to conduct this study to stress the development of soft skills among pupils and ascertain its influence to their learning competence.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the implication of developing soft skills to pupils' learning competence in Camaman-an Elementary School- Macapaya Extension in the City Division of Cagayan de Oro for the school year 2023-2024. Specifically, the study sought to

answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of development of soft skills among pupils in Camaman-an Elementary School- Macapaya Extension in the City Division of Cagayan de Oro in terms of;
 - 1.1. personal skills;
 - 1.2. social skills; and,
 - 1.3. communication skills?
2. What is the level of leaning competence of Grade 6 pupils when they are categorized as;
 - 2.1. outstanding;
 - 2.2. very satisfactory;
 - 2.3. satisfactory;
 - 2.4. fairly satisfactory;
 - 2.5. did not meet expectations?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of learning competence of Grade 6 pupils and the extent of developing soft skills of Grade 6 pupils?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized the descriptive-correlational research design. Descriptive research according to Calderon, et al (2019) is a fact-finding inquiry or investigation. It is employed to develop a thorough knowledge of the primary causes of the given situations.

In addition, descriptive-correlational design as an inquiry used an in-depth analysis of the problem which data collection methods include, but not limited to the survey questionnaire and the like.

Subsequently, descriptive-correlational research design is used to quantify the problem by way of generating numerical data or data that can be transformed into usable statistics. This method measures variables through the use of quantifiable or finite data and the analysis was based on generated information from statistical tools. This method is also used in an inquiry with larger population.

Successively, descriptive data gathering procedures comprise different types of gathering information such as, but not limited to, the use of adopted survey questionnaires.

Respondents

The respondents of the study are the Grade 6 pupils of Camaman-an Elementary School of the City Division of Cagayan de Oro.

There were fifty-four (54) pupil-respondents of the study who answered the survey questionnaire on the soft skills. The respondents were purposively chosen for the convenient accessibility of the researcher.

Instrument

The study utilized a survey questionnaire adopted from Tan (2020) who conducted a study on soft skills learning and development among public elementary school learners in Northern Mindanao, Philippines.

The survey instrument is composed of two (2) major components. The first component is on the soft skills development of public elementary school pupils with sixty (60) indicators categorized under three major components; namely; personal, social and communication soft skills. Part 2 is on pupils' learning achievements categorized as outstanding, very satisfactory, satisfactory, fairly satisfactory, and did not meet expectations.

Procedure

The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent through the recommendation of the Dean of the Graduate School and thesis adviser to conduct the study in the City Division of Cagayan de Oro.

The same permission was asked by the researcher to the parents of Grade 6 pupils to allow their child participate in the conduct of the study and utilize their learning competence based on their grades in the study. However, the parents were assured that the data gathered from the survey questionnaire be treated to its highest confidentiality and for educational purposes only.

After the respondents provided the data, the researcher retrieved the said questionnaire, summarized, tabulated, and submitted for analysis to the Statistician using appropriate statistical tools and techniques.

Data Analysis

The following statistical treatment were utilized in the study;

Problem 1. Mean value and standard deviation were used to present the extent of soft skills of Grade 6 pupils.

Problem 2. Frequency counts and percentages were used to present the level of pupils' learning competence.

Problem 3. Pearson-Product Moment Correlation was utilized to ascertain significant relationship between the extent of soft skills and the level of pupils' learning competence.

Results and Discussion

This section comprises the analysis, presentation, and interpretation of the finding resulting from this study on developing softskills in public elementary schools and its implication to pupils' learning competence. The analysis and interpretation of data is carried out based on the results of a survey questionnaire in lieu of the problems presented.

Problem 1. What is the extent of development of softskills among pupils in public elementary schools in Cagayan de Oro City in terms of the following; Personal skills, Social skills, and Communication skills?

Softs skills are relevant part of enhancing pupils' ability to work with other learners and to develop positive influence on intensifying their academic activities. Softskills are important in improving pupils' learning performance as they will enhance pupils' ability to communicate, share ideas, and work towards common goals as essential in creating an effective and efficient academic and learning competence.

Table 1.1 presents the mean distribution of pupils' softskills development in terms of personal skills.

Table 1.1. Mean Distribution of Softskills Development of Pupils in Terms of Personal Skills

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1. Personal skill is taught to enhance pupil's self-awareness	4.35	.799	Very Highly Developed
2. Personal skill is taught to enhance pupil's self-control.	4.33	.793	Very Highly Developed
3. Personal skill is taught to develop personal skill to cope with others in peace.	4.33	.793	Very Highly Developed
4. Personal skill is taught to develop pupil's emotional intelligence.	4.12	.712	Highly Developed
5. Personal skill is taught to develop pupil's motivation in learning.	4.04	.710	Highly Developed
6. Personal skill is taught to develop pupil's ability to understand oneself social-awareness.	3.85	.766	Highly Developed
7. Personal skill is taught to develop pupil's personal influence.	3.71	.764	Highly Developed
8. Personal skill is taught to develop[personal ability to collaborate in teamwork and group activities.	3.53	.696	Highly Developed
9. Personal skill is taught to enhance pupil's ability to relate with others.	3.28	.662	Moderately Developed
10. Personal skill is taught to develop pupil's listening competencies.	3.08	.775	Moderately Developed
11. Personal skill is taught to enhance pupil's self-worth.	3.11	.790	Moderately Developed
12. Personal skill is taught to enhance pupil's self-regulation.	3.04	.788	Moderately Developed
13. Personal skill is taught to develop pupil's personal skills to cooperate with others.	2.83	.867	Moderately Developed
14. Personal skill is taught to develop pupil's personal skills to understand their feelings and attitudes.	2.65	.814	Moderately Developed
15. Personal skill is taught to develop pupil's personal attachments to learning.	2.54	.755	Less Developed
16. Personal skill is taught to develop pupil's personal awareness of their roles in learning.	2.50	.756	Less Developed
17. Personal skill is taught to develop or enhance pupil's ability to consider others.	2.32	.988	Less Developed
18. Personal skill is taught to develop pupil's personal skills to contribute effort to achieve school's goals.	2.22	.950	Less Developed
19. Personal skill is taught to develop pupil's personal conviction to take responsibility in school activities.	2.28	.965	Less Developed
20. Personal skill is taught to develop pupil's personal skills of developing class camaraderie.	2.20	.942	Less Developed
Overall Mean	3.22	.804	Moderately Developed

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very Highly Developed/3.41-4.20 Highly Developed/2.61-3.40 Moderately Developed/1.81-2.60 Less Developed/1.00-1.80 Not Developed

Table 1.1 displays the mean distribution of the pupils' softskills in terms of personal skills. Overall, the respondents rated all the indicators as "Moderately Developed" with a mean of 3.22 (SD=.804). This indicates that teachers integrate in their teaching the development of pupils' personal skills which develop personal attributes such as the ability to communicate effectively, adaptability, emotional intelligence, and the capacity to learn effectively. It can be inferred based on findings that teachers taught personal skills to develop pupils' ability to relate with others, develop self-worth and self-regulation, ability to cooperate and collaborate with other learners.

Garcia and Benitez-Selliro (2022) averred that the development of pupils' softskills in terms of personal skills such as the ability to relate with fellow learners, listening to others, developing self-worth or self-respect and self-confidence, personal attributes to understand the attitudes and feelings of others are important personal attributes and skills to succeed in pupils' academic journey and enhancing their learning competence.

The indicator which states that "Personal skills is taught to enhance pupil's self-awareness" obtained the highest mean of 4.35 (SD=.799) which is verbally described as "Very Highly Developed". The result indicates that pupils extremely developed self-awareness or the ability to tune in to their feelings, thoughts, and actions. They are aware of their strengths and challenges and

understand how they see themselves may be different from how others see them.

Tan, et al (2021) asserted that pupils with higher personal skills can easily work with their peers and classmates in school and learning activities. They are critical to pupils' academic success as they allow them to work well their academic activities and with the fellow-learners. Pupils with strong personal skills can communicate ideas clearly and listen well to others. Additionally, Isaac (2021) argued that personal skills are considered important for pupils as it helps with their overall academic development and growth. Some of the most popularly acclaimed personal skills are adaptability, self-motivation, problem-solving, soft and interpersonal skills.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 2.20 (SD=.942) is verbally described as "Less Developed" in the indicators "Personal skill is taught to develop pupil's personal skills of developing class camaraderie". The result implies that teachers less emphasized companionship, fellowship, and comradeship in the class. It is imperative for teachers to develop intensify the teaching and development of personal skills of developing personal relationships or camaraderie in the class.

It can also be inferred based on findings that teachers do not emphasized the development of pupils' camaraderie or close relationship within the classroom because the teaching focuses only on the mastery of basic and least mastered learning competencies.

Sales (2021) pointed out that teaching of pupils' camaraderie or strong team camaraderie is critical. The sense of friendship and trust is the secret ingredient enabling high functioning teams to collaborate, innovate, communicate respectfully, share new or risky ideas freely, disagree amicably, and continuously learn higher and improve learning competence.

Table 1.2 presents the development of softs kills in terms of social skills of public elementary school pupils.

Table 1.2. Mean Distribution of Softskills Development of Pupils in Terms of Social Skills

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1. Social skills is taught to enhance pupil's social awareness.	4.40	.799	Very Highly Developed
2. Social skill is taught to enhance pupil's ability to work with others.	4.31	.793	Very Highly Developed
3. Social skill is taught to cope with others in peace.	4.31	.793	Very Highly Developed
4. Social skill is taught to develop pupil's social intelligence.	4.22	.721	Very Highly Developed
5. Social skill is taught to develop pupil's ability to collaborate with others in learning.	4.11	.711	Highly Developed
6. Social skill is taught to develop pupil's awareness of the social world.	4.01	.766	Highly Developed
7. Social skill is taught to develop pupil's social influence.	3.88	.764	Highly Developed
8. Social skill is taught to develop teamwork and collaboration.	3.71	.696	Highly Developed
9. Social skill is taught to develop pupil's ability to recognize that other students are equally important.	3.60	.662	Highly Developed
10. Social skill is taught to develop pupil's ability to treat fairly other students in the class.	3.40	.775	Moderately Developed
11. Social skill is taught to enhance pupil's ability to relate well with others in the school environment.	3.35	.790	Moderately Developed
12. Social skill is taught to enhance pupil's self-worth	3.28	.788	Moderately Developed
13. Social skill is taught to cope with others in peace.	3.22	.867	Moderately Developed
14. Social skill is taught to develop pupil's ability to socialize with others.	3.08	.814	Moderately Developed
15. Social skill is taught to develop pupil's motivation to learn with others.	2.98	.755	Moderately Developed
16. Social skill is taught to develop pupil's ability to trust others.	2.77	.756	Moderately Developed
17. Social skill is taught to develop pupil's social-interactive skills.	2.71	.988	Moderately Developed
18. Social skill is taught to develop cooperation and relationship with fellow students.	2.40	.950	Less Developed
19. Social skill is taught to develop pupil's ability to reciprocate to other's good deeds.	2.38	.965	Less Developed
20. Social skill is taught to develop pupil's ability to respect others.	2.28	.942	Less Developed
Overall Mean	3.42	.805	Highly Developed

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very Highly Developed/3.41-4.20 Highly Developed/2.61-3.40 Moderately Developed/1.81-2.60 Less Developed/1.00-1.80 Not Developed

Table 1.2 displays the mean distribution of the pupils' softskills in terms of social skills. Overall, the respondents rated all the indicators as "Highly Developed" with a mean of 3.42 (SD=.805). This indicates that teachers integrate in their teaching the development of pupils' social skills which develop social attributes such as the pupils' ability to interact and communicate with others. They include verbal and non-verbal communication such as speech and gestures. It can also be inferred that developing social skills is about being aware of emotions and communication patterns and using them effectively in different situations with other learners.

Ylagan and Aaron (2021) pointed out that social skills are vital softskills such as pupils' ability to speak clearly, make choices among alternatives, self-motivation, ability to lead and cooperate with others, develop team work, and solve problems and the like predict effective and efficient pupils' learning performance.

The indicator which states that "Social skills is taught to enhance pupil's social awareness" obtained the highest mean of 4.40 (SD=.799) which is verbally described as "Very Highly Developed". The result indicates that pupils extremely developed social-awareness or the ability to take the perspective of and empathize with others, including those from diverse backgrounds and cultures.

It can also be inferred that highly developed softskills in terms of social awareness allow pupils to focus on recognizing and understanding others' feelings. Social awareness, according Tan, et al (2021) avowed that pupils with higher social skills can easily work with their peers in classroom tasks. They are also critical to pupils' academic success as they allow them to work well with their

academic activities and with the fellow-learners. Pupils with strong social skills can communicate ideas clearly and listen well to others.

Isaac (2021) argued that social skills just like pupil's personal skills are considered important for their overall academic development and growth. Some of the most popularly acclaimed social skills are the ability to communicate and understand others.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 2.28 (SD=.942) is verbally described as "Less Developed" in the indicators "Social skill is taught to develop pupil's ability to respect others". The result implies that teachers less emphasized the teaching of reverence, administration, and veneration for others. It is, therefore, imperative for teachers to teach and emphasized respect with others in the classroom.

Sales (2021) pointed out that teaching respect to pupils will develop social relationship, camaraderie, and understanding which inspire collaboration and strong teamwork. Additionally, it was emphasized that a classroom environment where there is respect will create friendship and trust.

Table 1.3 presents the development of softskills in terms of communication skills of public elementary school pupils.

Table 1.3. *Mean Distribution of Softskills Development of Pupils in Terms of Communication Skills*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
1. Communication skill is taught to enhance pupil's ability to express ideas and opinion to others.	4.48	.631	Very Highly Developed
2. Communication skill is taught to enhance pupil's ability to speak and convey information	4.37	.617	Very Highly Developed
3. Communication skill is taught to cope up with others in peaceful communication.	4.37	.617	Very Highly Developed
4. Communication skill is taught to develop pupil's ability to be concise in words and utterance	4.28	.725	Very Highly Developed
5. Communication skill is taught to develop pupil's ability to participate in communicative and conversational activities more confidently	4.14	.707	Highly Developed
6. Communication skill is taught to develop pupil's awareness that communication is important to succeed in school	3.98	.924	Highly Developed
7. Communication skill is taught to develop pupil's ability to understand and comprehend others	3.71	.903	Highly Developed
8. Communication skill is taught to develop pupils' ability to encode information correctly and accurately.	3.54	.810	Highly Developed
9. Communication skill is taught to develop pupil's ability to decode information correctly and accurately	3.92	.60	Highly Developed
10. Communication skill is taught to develop pupil's ability to convey information effectively and efficiently to the receiver of the message.	3.25	.792	Moderately Developed
11. Communication skill is taught to enhance pupil's ability to receive feedback or information effectively and efficiently	3.08	.756	Moderately Developed
12. Communication skill is taught to enhance pupil's ability to participate effectively in oral discourse	2.85	.707	Moderately Developed
13. Communication skill is taught to cope up with pupils' inability to communicate	2.82	.680	Moderately Developed
14. Communication skill is taught to develop pupil's ability to effectively communicate in social setting.	2.77	.745	Moderately Developed
15. Communication skill is taught to develop pupil's ability to listen with others.	2.65	.849	Moderately Developed
16. Communication skill is taught to develop pupil's ability to communicate in multilingual classroom.	2.34	.915	Less Developed
17. Communication skill is taught to develop pupil's communicative-interactive skills	2.40	.969	Less Developed
18. Communication skill is taught to develop understanding of non-verbal signals in communication	2.31	1.034	Less Developed
19. Communication skill is taught to develop pupil's ability to process information received from others	2.34	1.127	Less Developed
20. Communication skill is taught to develop pupil's ability to use non-verbal expressions for effective communication	2.34	1.127	Less Developed
Overall Mean	3.30	.812	Moderately Developed

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very Highly Developed/3.41-4.20 Highly Developed/2.61-3.40 Moderately Developed/1.81-2.60 Less Developed/1.00-1.80 Not Developed

Table 1.3 displays the mean distribution of the pupils' softskills in terms of communication skills. Overall, the respondents rated all the indicators as "Moderately Developed" with a mean of 3.30 (SD=.812). This indicates that teachers assimilate in their teaching the development of pupils' communication skills which develop their ability to effectively communicate, understand and listen to each other, and express ideas as well as participate in any communicative and conversational activities. It can also be inferred that developing communication skills is about being able to develop understanding through communication and help pupils overcome diversities, build trust and respect, and create conditions for sharing creative ideas and solving problems.

Ylagan and Aaron (2021) pointed out that communication skills are vital softskills such as pupils' ability to speak clearly, make choices among alternatives, self-motivation, ability to lead and cooperate with others, develop team work, and solve problems and the like predict effective and efficient pupils' learning performance.

The indicator which states that “Communication skill is taught to enhance pupil’s ability to express ideas and opinion to others” obtained the highest mean of 4.48 (SD=.631) which is verbally described as “Very Highly Developed”. The result indicates that pupils extremely developed their communicative skills or their ability to express their ideas and opinion to others.

It can be deduced based on findings that highly developed softskills in terms of communication skills allow pupils to express and better understand their classmates and the learning situations. It helps pupils overcome diversities. Tan, et al (2021) emphasized that pupils with higher communication skills can easily work with their peers in classroom tasks. They are also critical to pupils’ academic success as they allow them to communicate well with classmates for their academic activities. Pupils with strong communication skills can communicate and express their ideas freely.

Isaac (2021) argued that communication skills just like pupil’s personal skills are considered important for their overall academic development and growth. Some of the most popularly acclaimed communication skills are the ability to communicate and create conditions for sharing creative ideas.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 2.31 (SD= 1.034) is verbally described as “Less Developed” in the indicators “Communication skills is taught to develop understanding of non-verbal signals in communication”. The result implies that pupils less developed their ability to understand the non-verbal signals in communication. Thus, it is imperative that teachers should intensify the teaching of non-verbal signals in communication.

Sales (2021) pointed out that developing communication skills will develop personal and social relationships, camaraderie, and understanding which inspire collaboration and strong teamwork. Additionally, it was emphasized that communication creates a classroom environment where learners learn how to listen, noticing both verbal and non-verbal cues and help better understand learners and the situation.

Problem 2. What is the level of learning competence of Grade 6 pupils when categorized as; Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Fairly Satisfactory, and Did not meet expectation?

Pupils’ learning competence is measured in terms of mastery of the learning competencies and the development of essential skills required for success in academic activities. Learning competence is categorized as outstanding, very satisfactory, satisfactory, fairly satisfactory, and did not meet expectations. Table 2.1 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of pupils’ learning competence.

Table 2.1. *Frequency Distribution of Pupils’ Learning Competence*

<i>Pupils’ Learning Competence</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Outstanding	5	7%
Very Satisfactory	31	44%
Satisfactory	32	46%
Fairly Satisfactory	2	3%
Did not meet expectation	0	0%
Total	70	100%

As seen, 32 (46%) of Grade 6 pupils were rated “Satisfactory” in their learning competence. This means that there were more pupils who performed reasonably or satisfactorily in their academic activities. Thus, it is imperative for the teachers to utilize instructional materials that are develop pupils’ softskills so that they can easily understand and work collaboratively with other learners in the classroom. As pointed out by Moira, et al (2020), pupils can have better and deep understanding of the lessons taught in the classrooms through their personal and social involvement with their classmates or peers and teachers. Their presentation skills also will be improved, and they set examples for self-expression. Therefore, the prominence and necessity of soft skills are commonly discussed topics in the field of research and education. Soft skill development has become the need both for personal, social, and academic development of pupils especially in the public schools.

On the contrary, 2 (3%) of the pupil-respondents manifest “Fairly Satisfactory” learning competence. This implies that only few Grade 6 pupils achieved equitably and reasonably in their academic subjects. It can be inferred that the teaching of softskills has improved pupils’ learning competence as they are only very minimal number of leaners who performed fairly satisfactory which means that the development of softskills influenced pupils’ learning performance. Thus, only 2 out of 70 Grade 6 pupils achieved fairly satisfactory (Grades from 75% to 79%) in all learning areas.

Problem 3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of pupils’ learning competence and the extent of pupils’ softskills development in terms of personal, social, and communication skills?

Table 3 presents the test of relationship between the pupils’ learning competence and the extent of pupils’ softskills development in terms of personal, social, and communication skills.

Table 3 displays the results of the test of relationship between the level of pupils’ learning competence and the extent of pupils’ softskills development in terms of personal, social, and communication skills. Results revealed that the personal skills have “negligible correlation” to pupils’ learning competence ($r=.032$) as indicated in the significant value of .793. This result indicates that the

development of personal skills among grade 6 pupils “negligibly correlated” to pupils’ learning competence. Thus, null hypothesis which states that “there is no significant relationship between the level of pupils’ learning competence and the extent of pupils’ softskills development in terms of personal skills” is accepted. It can be inferred based on findings that pupils’ learning competence cannot be attributed to pupils’ personal skills.

Table 3. *Test of Relationship between the Level of Pupils’ Learning Competence and the Extent of Pupils’ Softskills Development in terms of Personal, Social, and Communication Skills*

Soft skills Development	(r)	Sig 2-tailed	Pupils’ Learning Competence	
			Interpretation	Decision on Hol
Personal Skills	.032	.793	Denotes Negligible correlation	Accepted
Social Skills	.141	.245	Denotes Negligible Correlation	Accepted
Communication Skills	.100	.410	Denotes Negligible Correlation	Accepted

*significant at $p < 0.05$ alpha level

This finding was contrasting to that of Ciappei (2021) who found out that personal traits of an individual persuade his competencies. Personal skills are indefinitely carried from the moral aspect of life as significant traits nurtures learning competence of students.

Further, pupils’ social skills “negligibly correlated” to pupils’ learning competence ($r = .141$) as indicated in the significant value of .245. This result implies that the development of social skills among grade 6 pupils do not influence or affect pupils’ learning competence. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that “there is no significant relationship between the level of pupils’ learning competence and the extent of pupils’ softskills development in terms of social skills” is accepted. It can be deduced based on findings that pupils’ learning competence cannot be attributed to pupils’ social skills.

This finding was dissimilar to that of Heckman (2021) who argued that social skills of an individual predict pupils’ learning competence. Social skills are indefinitely carried from the moral aspect of life as significant traits nurtures learning competence of learners.

Moreover, the development of pupils’ softskills in terms of communication skills “negligibly correlated” to pupils’ learning competence ($r = .100$) as indicated in the significant value of .410. This result implies that the development of communication skills among grade 6 pupils do not stimulate pupils’ learning competence. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that “there is no significant relationship between the level of pupils’ learning competence and the extent of pupils’ softskills development in terms of communication skills” is accepted. It can be construed based on findings that pupils’ learning competence cannot be attributed to their communication skills.

This finding was incongruent to the findings of Chang and Nezu (2021) who argued that development of pupils’ communication skills predicts academic and learning performance.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

Pupils’ personal skills are regarded as primary skills used in predicting learning competence and school performance of learners in the basic education. The development of personal skills promotes awareness in terms of pupils’ personal skills such as their ability to get along well with other learners or their peers in the classroom, personal relationship with teachers and other members of the school community which according to researches benefits pupils especially in improving their academic and learning performance as well as in their engagements in school activities.

Pupils’ softskills development in terms of the social characteristics is said to promote behavior that facilitates understanding and adaptation of the variety of social settings. Social skills are considered as the primary variable for the relationship formation and the quality of social interactions each pupil has to perform as member of the social institution in order to optimize the social-emotional learning which influence success. Social skills help improve pupils’ social relations and personal well-being as well as their adjustments in school and classrooms atmosphere which lead to learning success and academic achievement.

The development of pupils’ softskills in terms of communication skills is presumed to be contributory to pupils’ improve learning competence and school engagements. Communication skill helps promote interactive relationships which has a direct influence on the quality of interpersonal relationships of pupils in the classroom. It also helps pupils to easily relate and interact with others in the school environment and facilitate an improved learning performance.

Based on the findings and conclusions presented, the following recommendations are suggested:

Department of Education (DepEd) Officials will encourage teachers to provide instructional intervention materials responsive to the development of learning competencies of public school pupils and at the same time instructional materials that proved teachers’ mastery of the subject matter and competence in crafting intervention materials to address learning challenges.

School Principals/School Heads will inspire teachers to develop their strategic intervention materials to address pupils’ learning challenges and needs. The intervention materials should be the results of research on inclusive needs of pupils and the crafted should

be evaluated and properly packaged for utilization.

Teachers as Instructional Leaders are recommended to continuously develop their strategic intervention materials which is responsive to the learning challenges of pupils to improve pupils' learning competence.

Parents are recommended to always provide the needed support in their children's learning activities and ensure parent-teachers collaboration in the education of their children. They are also enjoined to provide an inclusive support to their children's education through the provision of learner-centered home school learning environment.

Community Officials/Other stakeholders are recommended to always support and provide the needed logistical assistance to the school especially in the utilization available community resources.

Future Researchers are encouraged to conduct a similar investigation that thoroughly explore the functionality and utilization of strategic instructional materials that improve pupils' learning competence through the pupils' softskills development.

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